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Artificial Intelligence And Machine Learning As Emerging Tools In Modern Accounting Firms In Asaba, Delta State

Okoye, Danile Chukwuebuka & Prof. Onuora K. Joshua

Department of Accountancy,
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam, Anambra State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The study examined the artificial intelligence and machine learning as emerging tools in modern accounting firms in Asaba, Delta State. The study specific objectives are to: determine the effect of artificial intelligence on modern accounting firms in Asaba, Delta State; ascertain the effect of machine learning on modern accounting firms in Asaba, Delta State. This research work will be anchored on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Data were generated from primary sources. The method for data collection was questionnaire which was administered randomly among the staff of the selected audit firms in Asaba Delta state. The population of the study was ninety-one (91) staff. The hypotheses were tested using multiple regression analysis method at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that Artificial intelligence has significant effect on modern accounting firms in Asaba, Machine learning has significant effect on modern accounting firms in Asaba. The study concludes that that both Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning are powerful, emerging tools that positively shape the future of accounting practice in Asaba. Their continued adoption will be critical in ensuring that accounting firms remain relevant, efficient, and innovative in a rapidly evolving technological landscape. The study recommended that; Modern accounting firms in Asaba should invest more in Artificial Intelligence tools such as automated accounting software, intelligent auditing systems, and AI-driven financial reporting platforms. This will enhance efficiency, reduce human error, and improve overall service delivery. Accounting firms should integrate Machine Learning algorithms into their operations, particularly for financial forecasting, risk assessment, and fraud detection. ML systems can analyze large volumes of financial data more accurately and quickly than traditional methods

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, machine learning, emerging tools, modern accounting firms

1.1 INTRODUCTION

In the era of digitalization, rapid technological advances have transformed various fields, including accounting. Rapid technological developments have led to many innovations, such as Artificial Intelligence. Artificial intelligence or AI has transformed conventional accounting practices into more modern ones because it can improve efficiency, accuracy, and decision-making capabilities (Judijanto & Mulyadi, 2025). Donleavy (2022) also emphasizes that accounting must continue to adapt to social, economic, and technological changes in order to remain relevant to the needs of stakeholders. In this context, the application of technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) has given rise to a new paradigm in which the process of collecting, processing, and presenting financial information can be done more quickly and accurately.

In the accounting conceptual framework (ACF), this implies two characteristics: relevance and accurate representation (Donleavy, 2018). This is also in line with the statement by Fitriana et al. (2025) that the conceptual framework balances accurate representation and relevance to provide information that is useful to users of financial statements. Relevance in financial decisions means covering all information that is important to users, and accurate representation requires completeness, so that reports must provide sufficient descriptions of events and transactions so that users can make decisions based on accurate information.

Incorporating Artificial Intelligence (AI) does enable efficient data integration, but its application in accounting still poses challenges. AI raises issues regarding the concepts of relevance and representation. In fact, some information generated by AI does not always reflect the actual conditions. Furthermore, even though AI is rich in data, there is still uncertainty as to whether the results provided by AI meet the basic principles of accounting, and how to ensure that the results of AI-based systems continue to meet the qualitative characteristics of financial statements, namely relevance and representation (Yusuf et al, 2023).

Modern organizations generate large volumes of financial data that require efficient processing and analysis. AI and ML technologies enable accountants to process large datasets quickly and accurately, thereby improving efficiency and reducing human errors. Automated accounting software powered by AI can perform repetitive tasks such as data entry, invoice processing, bank reconciliation, and payroll preparation with minimal human intervention. This allows accountants to focus more on strategic decision-making and advisory roles rather than routine bookkeeping tasks (Sari, 2024).

Furthermore, AI and ML enhance the quality of financial reporting by improving accuracy and timeliness. Machine learning algorithms can identify unusual patterns and anomalies in financial transactions, which help in detecting fraud and financial irregularities. This capability is particularly important in modern business environments where financial crimes and corporate fraud have become increasingly sophisticated (Ekuma, 2023). The adoption of AI and ML in accounting has also improved auditing practices. Intelligent audit systems can analyze entire datasets instead of relying on sampling techniques, thereby increasing the reliability of audit results. Predictive analytics powered by machine learning can assist organizations in forecasting financial trends and managing risks more effectively.

The accounting profession is undergoing rapid transformation due to technological advancement, particularly the emergence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) as innovative tools in modern accounting systems. Traditionally, accounting practices relied heavily on manual processes and conventional accounting software, which are often time-consuming, prone to human error, and limited in handling large volumes of financial data. However, the increasing complexity of financial transactions and the demand for timely and accurate financial reporting have made traditional accounting approaches inadequate in meeting modern business needs. Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning technologies have the potential to automate routine accounting tasks such as data entry, transaction classification, fraud detection, financial forecasting, and audit processes. These technologies improve efficiency, accuracy, and decision-making by analyzing large datasets quickly and identifying patterns that may not be easily detected by human accountants.

Despite these advantages, the adoption of AI and ML in accounting systems, particularly in developing economies like Nigeria, remains relatively low. Many organizations still depend on traditional accounting methods due to factors such as lack of technological infrastructure, inadequate technical skills, high implementation costs, and resistance to change among accounting professionals. As a result, accounting systems in many firms continue to experience inefficiencies, delays in financial reporting, and increased risk of errors and fraud. Furthermore, there is limited empirical evidence on the extent to which AI and Machine Learning have improved accounting practices and organizational performance, especially in the Nigerian context.

This creates uncertainty among practitioners and policymakers regarding the practical benefits and challenges associated with integrating these technologies into accounting systems. Therefore, the problem of this study is to examine the role of Artificial Intelligence and Machine

Learning as emerging tools in modern accounting systems, with a view to determining their effectiveness, adoption level, and impact on accounting efficiency and financial reporting accuracy.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study is to examine artificial intelligence and machine learning as emerging tools in modern accounting firms in Asaba, Delta State. The specific objectives of the study were as follow:

1. Determine the effect of artificial intelligence on modern accounting firms in Asaba, Delta State.
2. Ascertain the effect of machine learning on modern accounting firms in Asaba, Delta State.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Conceptual review

2.1.1. Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has brought a new paradigm in data and information management by automating processes, analyzing data on a large scale, and even predicting trends, thereby potentially revolutionizing the way information systems work (Pribadi & Dewayanto, 2025). Artificial intelligence is a technology used in various industries and institutions to improve operational efficiency and effectiveness and drive innovation to provide good service to users (Tampubolan & Dewayanto, 2025). AI has three basic concepts that generate extraordinary innovation, including big data, which involves collecting and analyzing large amounts of data to find patterns and trends. Furthermore, according to Indriani (2025), AI encompasses various technologies such as machine learning, natural language processing, and pattern recognition. Therefore, AI has grown to become a major force in technological transformation, and its use in software development is increasingly important.

In a theoretical context, AI is seen as part of the evolution of information rationalization in line with the goals of modern accounting namely, providing relevant and reliable information for decision makers. AI, in Donleavy's (2018) accounting theory perspective, serves as a means to strengthen principles through more accurate data presentation and expand the relevance of information by providing machine learning-based predictions. Thus, the application of AI is not only a technological innovation but also a logical consequence of the development of information theory within the conceptual framework of modern accounting. The link between AI and accounting is getting stronger as the business world needs faster and more accurate financial reporting. The accounting sector, which plays a role in recording and analyzing company financial activities, has felt the significant impact of this technology (Jernih. & Laksono, 2025).

AI technology, which includes machine learning algorithms, is now used to automate routine tasks such as data entry and transaction categorization, which were previously the basis of traditional accounting practices. Furthermore, with machine learning supporting more efficient decision-making through big data analysis and machine learning algorithms that improve prediction accuracy, it is important for forecasting and strategic planning (Judijanto & Mulyadi, 2025). Donleavy (2022) adds that the role of AI in accounting is not only technical but also conceptual. This is because, within the framework of accounting theory, AI supports the main objectives of financial reporting by generating relevant, reliable, and comparable information.

With AI's ability to manage big data and perform predictive analysis, the concepts of relevance and representation take on new meaning, namely not only describing the past but also predicting possible futures. According to Deby et al. (2025), modern accounting uses a continuous model that processes financial data in real-time. From the above explanation, it can be concluded that AI minimizes the risk of human error through fast and accurate data processing, supporting the provision of real-time financial information for responsive decision-making.

2.1.2 Machine Learning

Machine learning (ML) is a subfield of artificial intelligence (AI) that involves the development of algorithms and models that enable computers to learn from data and improve their performance on tasks over time without being explicitly programmed (Alpaydin, 2020). Machine Learning has many applications in various fields, including image and speech recognition, natural language processing, recommendation systems, and fraud detection (Alpaydin, 2020). However, tasks previously done by

humans are now performed using artificial intelligence and Machine learning. When it comes to processing a massive amount of data, finding fraud by identifying unusual operations, communicating with customers online and performing other essential functions, the accounting profession has not fully embraced artificial intelligence and machine learning. For example, in voice recognition, there are several excellent use cases.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Technology Acceptance Theory (TAT)

Davis, Bagozzi, and Warshaw (1989) came up with the TAT model in a bid to explain the user's acceptance and intention in the use of technology. TAT looks at a technology perceived ease of use and usefulness. The perceived usefulness of a technology is the belief by the user that the technology will improve his or her on job performance. The perceived ease of use looks at how easily the user can learn to use the new system or the technology (Gefen et al., 2003). According to the model, if the new technology ease of use is achieved it is likely to positively lead to perceived usefulness. There are external variables like the environment that can affect the perceived ease of use and usefulness.

This theory is often used when researching on information technologies and its main emphasis is on the two perceptive factors. Liu and Arnett (2000) looked at the important factors affecting the developing of a website based on this model. Gefen et al. (2003) used both TAT and rust and came up with a more evolved model that could be used to explain the online behaviors of customers. Pavlou (2003) suggests the use of thee-commerce acceptance model on online customers that uses survey and experiment techniques. Horst, Kutts chreuter and Gutting (2007) did a follow up study that examined if it was prudent for the Netherlands government to use-government to serve its people like in other nations. The study considered TAT factors, faith, perceived risk and public experiences. The findings of the study showed that the public trusted the government and resonated with information technology. The empirical study further revealed that TAT is not only useful for examination of information technology but it also useful ion examining the acceptance of intention behavior related to information technology and further explains the behavior issues faced by online users of technology(Liu and Arnett, 2000; Gefen et al., 2003).

2.3 Empirical Review

Hossain, et al. (2025) explored the role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in enhancing Accounting Information Systems (AIS), focusing on both the benefits and challenges associated with its integration. Through a qualitative case study approach involving multiple industries, including banking, retail, manufacturing, and healthcare, the research examines real-world applications of AI technologies such as machine learning, robotic process automation, and predictive analytics. The findings reveal that AI significantly improves operational efficiency, financial reporting accuracy, decision-making, and cost savings. However, the adoption process is often hindered by technical integration issues, employee resistance, and concerns related to data privacy and ethical transparency. The study applies the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theory to interpret organizational responses to AI adoption. It concludes by emphasizing the need for robust governance frameworks, employee training, and sector-specific strategies to ensure responsible and effective implementation. This research provides practical insights for organizations seeking to modernize their AIS and outlines directions for future studies on the long-term and ethical integration of AI in accounting. Ehigie, Ehigie and Aghamioghogho (2025) evaluated the application of artificial intelligence and machine learning in accounting practice. The research design is a mixed-method approach that incorporates qualitative and quantitative methods. The study administered 60 questionnaires to extract responses from the selected sample size. The ordinary least squares regression techniques were employed to validate the research hypotheses. The regression output shows no significant relationship between robotic automation and accounting practice, it further reveals no significant relationship between algorithm development and accounting practice, and no significant relationship between model and accounting practice. The study recommends that accounting firms and organizations priorities investment in technology infrastructure to support the implementation of Robotic Process Automation (RPA) and advanced algorithms. This

includes upgrading hardware and software, and ensuring reliable internet connectivity. Government support through incentives or subsidies could also encourage wider adoption of these technologies.

Ashif and Wolters, K.(2025) explored the transformative impact of artificial intelligence on the accounting profession. The article shows how machine learning algorithms and natural language processing have revolutionized financial data analysis, enhancing pattern recognition capabilities and anomaly detection in financial statements. It shows the significant efficiency improvements in document review and data extraction achieved through NLP technologies, while highlighting how AI has fundamentally transformed budgeting and financial forecasting practices through sophisticated predictive modeling techniques. The article further examines automation in data ingestion and client file management, showcasing measurable improvements in efficiency and resource utilization. Additionally, the article looks toward future directions for AI in accounting, including emerging technologies, regulatory considerations, and implications for professional skill development, providing a comprehensive overview of how AI continues to reshape the accounting landscape.

Das, et al. (2026) analyzed the academic literature related to the impact of AI and machine learning technologies on the accounting and auditing professions. Primarily, it explores the opportunities, benefits, threats, and ethical challenges of implementing AI-based technologies in the context of various organizations. In this study, we have employed different analytical techniques and performed expert analysis to examine the trends in this field. This study finds that different AI tools play an important role in enhancing the quality of financial reports. Besides, AI helps stakeholders to make precise and accurate judgments. Moreover, AI has been found to be significant in reducing various accounting and auditing errors that reduce tax reporting quality and increase audit acceptance quality.

Loso, et al. (2025) examined the impact of AI and ML on the role of accountants and the responses of educational institutions and the profession to this digital transformation. The findings indicate the need for collaboration between educational institutions, professional organizations, and industry to overcome the challenges of technology adaptation. With joint efforts, the accounting profession can transform into a strategic partner in an increasingly complex and data-driven business world, while providing significant added value in modern financial management.

METHODOLOGY

Information on the existing state of the phenomenon was gathered through descriptive research in order to characterize "what exists" in relation to variables or conditions in a situation. It provides information and traits about the population or phenomenon under study. Because this study aims to gather data for its execution, a descriptive approach is consequently favored. The questionnaire served as the main data source for this investigation. This is due to the characteristics of the variables that were employed. The employees of the following Delta State auditing businesses made up the study's population. Ofili Kingsley & Co., Patrick Uzoka & Co., Olusola Peter & Co., Veronica Asem & Co., Grace Laya & Co., Sam Nwaulu & Co., Solomon Isaiah & Co., and Osakwe Samson & Co. This gives us ninety-one (91) staff. Employees of the companies being studied provide the researcher with original data. Top managers, supervisors, managers, and employees from the several companies under investigation made up the responders. A questionnaire was used to gather the data. The data questionnaire was chosen because it has a high response rate, simply has to be given to respondents to complete, requiring less time to administer, allows for anonymity, and gathers first-hand information. The questionnaire's closed-ended questions are used in the study. Multiple regression approaches were used to evaluate hypotheses at the significance level of 0.05.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple regression result was employed to test the effect of independent or explanatory variables on the dependent variables. The result of the multiple regression analysis is presented in the tables below.

Table 4.1.1 Summary of the Regression Result

The result of the multiple regressions formulated in chapter three is presented in the tables below

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.902 ^a	.662	.643	.11789	.162	8.583	3	88	.000	1.633

a. Predictors: (Constant), ARI, MAI

b. Dependent Variable: MAF

Table 4.1.1 shows that R² which measures the strength of the effect of independent variable on the dependent variable have the value of 0.66%. This implies that 90% of the variation on artificial intelligence and machine learning is explained by variations in modern accounting firms. This was supported by adjusted R² of 0.66%.

Test for autocorrelation: This is used test whether errors corresponding to different observation are uncorrelated. If the value of the durbin-watson from the regression result is close to 2 no autocorrelation in that regression result, but if it deviates significantly then there is autocorrelation. The Durbin-Watson statistic (D.W) of 1.6 reveals no autocorrelation in the models. Hence, the result is good for business analysis because the Durbin Watson result is 1.633

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.477	8	.119	8.583	.000 ^b
	Residual	2.474	88	.014		
	Total	2.951	91			

a. Dependent Variable: MAF

b. Predictors: (Constant), ARI, MAL

The f-statistics value of 8.583 in table above with f-statistics probability of 0.000 shows that the independent variables has significant effect on independent variables such as artificial intelligence and machine learning can collectively explain the variations in audit quality

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	.668	.076		8.780	.000	.518	.819
	ARI	.083	.019	.407	4.462	.000	.046	.120
	MAL	.043	.039	.207	2.462	.007	.023	.116

a. Dependent Variable: MAF

A’piori Criteria: This is determined by the existing accounting theories; it also indicates the signs and magnitude of the business parameter under review. In table above, we found out that Artificial intelligence has a positive sign given its value as .083; this implies that a unit increase in Artificial intelligence increases the modern accounting system by 8%, this conform to the a’ priori expectation. However, advance machine learning has a positive sign given its value as .043; this implies that a unit increase in machine learning increases the modern accounting firms by 43%, this conform to the a’ priori expectation

T- Statistics: The t-test is used to measure the individual statistical significance of our explanatory parameter in the model. From table Coefficients above Artificial intelligence is 4.462 this is statistically significant, this suggest that it contribute significantly to modern accounting firms at 5% level of significant. Machine learning is 2.462 this is statistically significant, this suggest that it contribute significantly to modern accounting firms at 5% level of significant.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

4.2.1 Test of Hypothesis One

H₀₂: Artificial Intelligence has no significant effect on modern accounting firms in Asaba.

In testing this hypothesis, the t-statistics and probability value in table above is used. Artificial intelligence has a t-statistics of 2.211 and a probability value of 0.020 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that Artificial intelligence has significant effect on modern accounting firms in Asaba.

4.2.2 Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₃: Machine learning has no significant effect on modern accounting firms in Asaba

Machine learning has a t-statistics of 5.078 and a probability value of .000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that Machine learning has significant effect on modern accounting firms in Asaba

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

This study examined the influence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) as emerging tools in modern accounting firms in Asaba. The findings reveal that both technologies have become indispensable drivers of innovation, efficiency, and competitive advantage within the accounting profession.

First, the research confirms that Artificial Intelligence has a significant positive impact on modern accounting firms in Asaba. AI technologies such as intelligent data processing, automated auditing systems, natural language processing, and predictive analysis—have enhanced data accuracy, reduced processing time, and minimized human errors. These improvements have allowed accounting professionals to focus on higher-level analytical tasks, decision-making, and client advisory services, thereby improving overall service quality and productivity.

Similarly, the study found that Machine Learning has significant positive effects on modern accounting firms in Asaba. Through ML algorithms, accounting firms are now better able to identify complex patterns in financial data, improve risk assessment, detect anomalies and fraud, and forecast future financial outcomes with higher precision. Machine learning's ability to continuously learn and adapt from data enables firms to refine their processes over time, further strengthening operational effectiveness.

Overall, the integration of AI and ML into accounting practices has transformed traditional methodologies, fostering greater accuracy, efficiency, and strategic insight. These technologies not only support routine tasks but also empower accounting professionals to deliver enhanced value to clients in an increasingly digital business environment. Therefore, modern accounting firms in Asaba that embrace AI and ML are likely to experience improved performance, reduced operational costs, and sustainable competitive growth.

In conclusion, this study underscores that both Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning are powerful, emerging tools that positively shape the future of accounting practice in Asaba. Their continued adoption will be critical in ensuring that accounting firms remain relevant, efficient, and innovative in a rapidly evolving technological landscape.

5.2 Recommendations

- i. Modern accounting firms in Asaba should invest more in Artificial Intelligence tools such as automated accounting software, intelligent auditing systems, and AI-driven financial reporting platforms. This will enhance efficiency, reduce human error, and improve overall service delivery.
- ii. Accounting firms should integrate Machine Learning algorithms into their operations, particularly for financial forecasting, risk assessment, and fraud detection. ML systems can analyze large volumes of financial data more accurately and quickly than traditional methods.

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